

PREDICTION OF SIDE EFFECTS OF DRUGS USING GRAPH NEURAL NETWORKS

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Abstract - Adverse Drug Reactions (ADRs) are a major problem in healthcare because some medicines may cause unexpected side effects. Detecting these effects early is important to reduce health risks and avoid failure during clinical trials. Traditional experimental methods require high cost and lot of time, and they may not identify rare side effects in the early stage. In this work, we use a Graph Neural Network (GNN) approach to predict potential drug side effects based on biomedical data. A knowledge graph is created by combining information about drugs, diseases, and known side-effects. Five datasets, namely drug names data, meddra all se, drug action labels data, drug disease labels data, and drug symptom labels data, are combined to build a knowledge graph. The Graph Convolutional Network (GCN) learns relationships between these entities and predicts new drug-side effect connections. The model also provides confidence scores to show how strongly a side effect is related to a drug. In addition, the system identifies the biological action type of drugs such as virus, bacteria, fungi, or human cell targets. The results show that graph-based learning can capture complex biomedical relationships effectively. This approach may help researchers identify risky drugs earlier and support safer drug development.

Keywords — Adverse Drug Reactions, Graph Neural Network, Graph Convolutional Network, Knowledge Graph, Drug Side Effect Prediction, Link Prediction, Drug Safety, Machine Learning in Healthcare.

I. INTRODUCTION

Medicines are an essential part of modern healthcare because they help in treating diseases and improving the quality of life. Along with their benefits many drugs may also cause unwanted effects known as Adverse Drug Reactions (ADRs). These side effects may be mild, such as headache or nausea, but in some cases they may become serious, such as heart attacks and become very dangerous to patient health. ADRs are one of the major reasons why many drugs fail during clinical trials, leading to waste of time, cost, and effort in the drug development process [1]. Because of this, identifying possible side effects at an early stage has become an important research problem.

Traditional approaches for identifying drug side effects mainly depend on laboratory experiments and clinical testing.

These methods require a lot of time and are very expensive. In addition, clinical trials are usually conducted on a limited number of participants, so rare or long-term side effects may not be observed early. As biomedical data has increased in recent years, researchers have started using computational methods to support early prediction of drug safety risks [2].

Drugs interact with different biological components such as proteins, genes, and cells inside the human body. These interactions form a complex network of relationships. Knowledge graphs are useful for representing such relationships because they organize biomedical information in the form of nodes and connections. Several public databases provide useful drug-related information, including drug properties, targets, and side effects, which can be used for research in drug safety prediction [3], [4].

Machine learning techniques are widely used to analyze the biomedical data. However, traditional machine learning models usually treat the data as independent values and may not properly capture the relationships between drugs and biological entities. Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) are more suitable for this type of data because they are designed to work with graph structures. GNN models learn by collecting information from connected nodes, which helps in understanding complex relationships between drugs and side effects [5], [6].

Recent studies have shown that combining multiple biomedical datasets can improve prediction performance. When chemical information, biological relationships, and clinical data are used together, the model can learn better patterns. Some times research has also focused on improving the transparency of predictions so that researchers can understand why a side effect may occur [7], [8].

In this work, a method based on Graph Neural Networks is used to predict possible side effects of drugs. A knowledge graph is created by combining drug names, meddra all se, drug action labels, drug disease labels, and drug symptom labels datasets. In this graph, drugs, diseases, and side effects are shown as nodes, while their relationships are represented as edges. A Graph Convolutional Network (GCN) model learns patterns from the graph and predicts possible connections between drugs and side effects using a link prediction approach. The system also identifies the biological action type of drugs, such as whether the drug mainly affects viruses, bacteria, fungi, or human cells.

The main goal of this work is to support the early identification of possible drug risks and improve the safety evaluation process. Predicting side effects before clinical testing may help reduce drug failure rates and support the development of safer medicines.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

A. Adverse Drug Reaction Studies and Biomedical Datasets

Adverse Drug Reactions (ADRs) have been widely studied because they directly affect patient safety and increase healthcare costs. Unexpected side effects are a major reason for drug failure during the clinical trials. Identifying these effects early can help lower risks and enhance the drug development process. Earlier studies mainly depended on laboratory experiments, animal testing, and observation of patient responses. Although these approaches provide useful results, they require significant time and cost. In many situations, rare side effects are not identified until the drug is used by a large population.

To support research in this field, several biomedical datasets have been developed. The SIDER database contains information about known drug side effects collected from medical records and drug labels [4]. DrugBank is another important resource that provides detailed information about drug properties, targets, and interactions [3]. These datasets allow researchers to study relationships between drugs and biological entities using computational techniques. The availability of such structured data has encouraged the use of machine learning methods for predicting drug safety.

B. Traditional Computational Methods for ADR Prediction

Initial computational approaches for ADR prediction mainly focused on similarity-based techniques. These methods assume that drugs with similar chemical structures or biological properties may produce similar side effects. Statistical learning models and matrix factorization methods were also used to estimate possible drug-side effect relationships.

Although these approaches produced useful results, they have limitations when handling complex biomedical data. Many traditional models treat features independently and do not fully consider relationships between drugs, proteins, genes, and diseases. In biological systems, drugs usually interact with multiple targets, which creates a network of relationships. Because traditional machine learning methods do not fully represent these connections, their prediction performance may decrease when the data becomes complex.

C. Graph Neural Network Based Approaches

Graph-based learning approaches have gained attention because biomedical data can naturally be represented as networks. In these networks, drugs, diseases, proteins, and side effects are connected to each other. Graph Neural

Networks (GNNs) are designed to handle such structured data. These models update node features by collecting information from neighboring nodes, which helps capture hidden relationships between entities [5].

Several studies have indicated that GNN-based models improve predictions of drug side effects. DruGNN combines various biological relationships, like drug-gene and gene-gene interactions, into a heterogeneous graph, achieving better prediction accuracy compared to traditional models [1]. Hybrid embedding approaches combine chemical structure information with biological interaction networks to improve learning capability [7]. These approaches show that combining multiple biomedical data sources helps the model understand complex patterns more effectively.

Graph neural networks have also been applied in related research areas such as drug-drug interaction prediction and drug-protein interaction prediction. Graph convolution models learn structural relationships between biological entities and help identify how drugs produce therapeutic effects or side effects [6]. Some studies also attempt to improve interpretability so that the prediction results can be better understood by researchers [8].

Even though graph-based approaches provide better performance, some challenges still exist. Biomedical datasets are often imbalanced, and rare side effects are difficult to predict accurately. Some models require large amounts of data and high computational resources, which may limit their practical usage.

D. Comparative Analysis of Existing Approaches

Various methods have been proposed in the literature to predict drug side effects, each with its own strengths and weaknesses. DruGNN is a graph-based model that incorporates multiple biological relationships like drug-gene and drug-drug interactions. By using heterogeneous biomedical data, it enhances prediction accuracy compared to traditional methods. However, the model offers limited interpretability, making it hard to understand how predictions are produced [1].

SIDER-based statistical approaches rely on real clinical side effect records collected from medical documents. These methods are useful because they are based on real observations, but they are not able to capture complex relationships between biomedical entities. As a result, their prediction capability becomes limited when indirect biological interactions are involved [4].

DrugBank similarity-based models use drug interaction data and chemical similarity information to predict side effects. These models benefit from the availability of large biomedical datasets. However, similarity-based approaches may fail to identify hidden patterns when drugs have different structures but similar biological effects [3].

Hybrid embedding graph neural network models combine chemical structure information with biological interaction networks. By integrating multiple features, these models

improve prediction performance. However, the increased number of features also increases model complexity and computational requirements [7].

Graph Convolutional Network (GCN) based approaches for drug–protein interaction prediction focus on learning structural relationships between biological entities. These models are effective in capturing network patterns but usually require large datasets for training, which may not always be available [6].

Explainable graph neural network models attempt to identify important molecular features responsible for drug effects. These models improve interpretability by showing which biological components contribute to side effects. However, the additional explainability mechanisms increase computational cost [8].

Compared with earlier approaches, this study applies a Graph Neural Network together with a knowledge graph constructed from drug names, meddra all se, drug action labels, drug disease labels, and drug symptom labels datasets. By integrating multiple biomedical relationships, the proposed method is able to learn complex patterns and perform link prediction to estimate possible side effects. However, the effectiveness of the model depends largely on the completeness and reliability of the available datasets.

E. Research Gap and Motivation

From the analysis of existing approaches, it is observed that many earlier models have certain limitations. Statistical and similarity-based approaches do not fully capture complex biological relationships. Traditional machine learning models improve performance but often ignore the network structure of biomedical data. Some graph-based models depend on limited datasets or require high computational resources.

Another challenge is the imbalance in biomedical datasets, where rare side effects appear less frequently. This will make it more difficult for models to learn patterns related to uncommon reactions. In addition, some methods provide predictions without clear explanation, which makes interpretation difficult.

Motivated by these limitations, the proposed work focuses on combining multiple biomedical datasets into a knowledge graph. The knowledge graph will represent the relationships between drugs, diseases, and side effects in a structured manner. A Graph Neural Network model is applied to learn patterns from this graph and predict possible drug side effects.

The main motivation of this work is to support early identification of potential risks using available biomedical data. Early prediction of side effects may help reduce failure during clinical trials and improve drug safety. By learning relationships from connected biomedical entities, the proposed model attempts to improve prediction reliability and support safer medicine development.

III. LITERATURE SURVEY

Several studies have been carried out in recent years to predict drug side effects using computational approaches. Early research mainly focused on statistical models and similarity-based techniques, where chemical structure similarity and biological similarity between drugs were used to estimate possible side effects. These approaches provided useful baseline results, but they were limited in capturing complex relationships between different biological entities.

Bongini et al. introduced DruGNN, a graph neural network framework that integrates multiple biological relationships including drug–gene, gene–gene, and drug–drug relationships into a heterogeneous graph structure. The model improves prediction performance when compared to traditional machine learning models. Their results showed that graph-based learning can effectively capture complex biomedical patterns [1].

The SIDER database contains organized information about drug side effects gathered from clinical reports and medical documents. This dataset has been widely used for studying relationships between drugs and adverse reactions. Several studies have applied SIDER data to build predictive models that estimate potential side effects based on previously reported clinical evidence [4].

DrugBank is another important biomedical resource that provides detailed information about drugs, including their chemical structure, targets, and interactions. The database has been used in many research works for studying drug interactions and predicting drug-related risks using computational models [3].

Yu et al. proposed a hybrid embedding graph neural network model that combines chemical structure features with biological interaction networks. By integrating multiple types of information, the model improves the learning capability and prediction performance for drug side effects. The study shows that combining structural and relational features can improve prediction accuracy [7].

Graph neural networks have also been applied in related biomedical problems such as drug–drug interaction prediction and drug–protein interaction prediction. Graph convolutional models can learn structural relationships between biological entities and identify hidden interactions that may lead to side effects. These models perform better than traditional methods when dealing with complex network data [6].

Recent studies have also explored explainable graph neural network models to understand the biological reason behind predicted drug reactions. These approaches try to identify important molecular components responsible for drug activity. Improving transparency helps researchers better understand the prediction results in machine learning systems [8].

Although many studies have shown promising results, some limitations still exist. Biomedical datasets are often

incomplete and imbalanced, which makes prediction of rare side effects difficult. Some models also require high computational resources and large datasets. Because of these challenges, there is still a need for improved models that can effectively learn from available biomedical data.

Based on the results from previous research works, this project focuses on integrating multiple datasets into a knowledge graph and apply graph neural network techniques for predict drug side effects. By learning connections among drugs, diseases, and their side effects, the proposed approach aims to improve prediction reliability and support safer drug development.

IV. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

A. System Architecture

The proposed system predicts possible drug side effects by learning relationships between biomedical entities using a Graph Neural Network model. The system integrates multiple datasets and converts them into a knowledge graph representation. The architecture is divided into several modules, where each module performs a specific function in the prediction process.

1. Data Collection Module

The data collection module gathers biomedical datasets containing information about drugs, diseases, and side effects. In this work, Five datasets are used are drug names, meddra all se, drug action labels, drug disease labels, and drug symptom labels.

These datasets provide structured information about relationships between drugs and biological conditions. Combining multiple datasets helps increase the amount of available information and supports more reliable prediction.

2. Data Preprocessing Module

Before Building the model, the collected data is processed to ensure consistency and usability. During preprocessing, missing values are handled, duplicate records are removed, and text data is standardized. Since the datasets come from different sources, preprocessing helps convert them into a common format. Each entity, including drugs, diseases, and side effects, is assigned a unique index value. This step allows the data to be efficiently represented in graph form and simplifies further processing.

3. Knowledge Graph Construction Module

After preprocessing, the data is transformed into a graph-based representation. The knowledge graph contains nodes and edges that represent relationships between biomedical entities.

Nodes represent the drugs, diseases and side effects. Edges represents the drug–disease relationships and drug–side effect relationships

The knowledge graph structure helps maintain connections between entities and provides meaningful input for the Graph Neural Network model.[5]

4. Graph Neural Network Module

The Graph Neural Network module learns patterns from the constructed knowledge graph. In this work, a Graph Convolutional Network (GCN) is applied to extract useful features from the graph structure. The GCN updates the representation of each node by combining information from its neighboring nodes.

By passing information through multiple layers, the model captures hidden relationships among drugs, diseases, and side effects [6]. The output of this stage is a set of node embeddings, which are numerical representations of biomedical entities that contain structural and relational information derived from the graph.

5. Model Training Module

In this module, the GNN model is trained using known relationships between the drugs and the side effects. The training process helps the model learn patterns that describe how drugs are connected to different biological conditions. Model parameters such as number of layers, learning rate, and training iterations are adjusted to improve performance. The objective of training is to generate embeddings that represent relationships accurately within the graph structure [7].

6. Link Prediction Module

The link prediction module predicts possible relationships between drug nodes and side effect nodes. Using the learned node embeddings, the model calculates a probability score that indicates how strongly a drug is related to a particular side effect. Higher prediction scores indicate stronger relationships. These scores help identify possible adverse drug reactions that may not be directly observed in the dataset [5].

7. Drug Action Classification Module

This module identifies the biological action category of drugs based on their associated diseases. Drugs are classified according to whether they mainly affect viruses, bacteria, fungi, or human cells. Understanding the biological action type helps provide additional insight into how drugs interact with biological systems. Similar classification approaches have been used in biomedical prediction studies to understand drug behavior [8].

8. User Interface Module

A simple user interface is developed using Streamlit to allow easy interaction with the system. Users can enter the name of a drug and obtain predicted side effects along with confidence scores. The interface also displays the biological action category of the drug. The interface helps present the results in a clear and understandable format.

9. Output Visualization Module

This module presents the results in a structured format. Predicted side effects, confidence scores, and drug classification results are displayed clearly so that users can easily understand the output. Visualization helps interpret model predictions and improves usability of the system.

Fig. 1. System Architecture Diagram for the proposed system

B. Problem Formulation

The task of predicting drug side effects can be viewed as a link prediction problem on a graph. The biomedical data is represented in the form of a graph:

$$G = (V, E)$$

where:

V denotes nodes such as drugs, diseases, and side effects

E denotes relationships between nodes

The Graph Neural Network learns node representations by combines the information from neighboring nodes. Using the learned embeddings, the model predicts the probability of a relationship between a drug node and a side effect node[5], [6].

If the predicted probability is high, then the model identifies a possible side effect for the drug. The objective of the model is to learn patterns from known relationships and apply this knowledge to predict unknown connections. This approach allows identification of possible adverse drug reactions using existing biomedical data [6].

V.MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

The interaction network establishes drug-to-adverse reaction relationships through its graph structure $G = (V, E)$ which operates as follows $V = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ defines drug and side effect nodes while E contains all edge connections between these elements. The adjacency matrix serves as the graph connection representation for the entire graph structure.

$A \in R^{n \times n}$, Here each entry indicates whether two nodes are connected, Where Each node v_i in the graph has the feature vector $x_i \in R^d$ which represents the specific drug or side effect characteristics associated with that node.

1. Graph Representation

In this work, biomedical data is represented as a graph structure. The graph contains nodes and edges that describe relationships between drugs, diseases, and side effects. Graph representation helps preserve the connections between biomedical entities and this will allow the model to learn relational information effectively.

The knowledge graph will be represented as:

$$G = (V, E)$$

Fig. 2. Basic graph structure $G(V, E)$ showing nodes and edges representing relationships between entities.

Where we can denote V as the set of nodes and E as denotes the set of edges

Here, Each node will represents a biomedical entity such as a drug, disease, or side effect. An edge represents the known relationship between those two entities. For example, a drug may be connected to a disease it treats or a side effect it may cause.

Those connections between the nodes are stored using an adjacency matrix :

$$A \in R^{n \times n}$$

Here, n indicates the total number of nodes in the graph. If two nodes are connected, the matrix value is 1, otherwise it is 0. Each node is described with a feature vector represented as:

$$X \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d}$$

Here, d denotes the number of features describing each node. These features provide information required for learning node representations. Graph based data representation has been widely used in biomedical research to capture complex interactions among drugs and its biological entities [5].

2. Graph Convolutional Network Learning

A Graph Convolutional Network (GCN) is applied to learn node embeddings from the knowledge graph. GCN works by aggregating information from its neighboring nodes and refining the feature values across multiple layers. This helps the model learn both structural and feature-based relationships between biomedical entities.

The propagation rule for a GCN layer can be written as:
 $H^{(l+1)} = \sigma(A^l H^{(l)} W^{(l)})$

Fig. 3. Architecture of the Graph Convolutional Network (GCN) model.

Here \hat{A} represents the normalized adjacency matrix and $H^{(l)}$ is represents the node feature matrix at layer l and $W^{(l)}$ is the trainable weight matrix, and σ denotes the activation function. Initially, the node features are given as $H^{(0)}=X$

After passing through multiple GCN layers, the model generates node embeddings that contain important structural information. Graph-based learning methods have shown strong performance in predicting biological interactions such as drug–target and drug–drug relationships [6].

3. Link Prediction for Side Effect Estimation

The prediction of drug side effects is framed as a link prediction problem.. The goal is to estimate the probability of a connection between the drug node and a side effect node. After obtaining node embeddings from the GCN model, the similarity between two nodes is calculated using the dot product is $\text{Score}(u,v) = \sigma(h_u^T h_v)$

Where h_u is represents as embedding of drug node and h_v is represents as embedding of side effect node and σ is represents sigmoid function.

The sigmoid function turns the output into a probability value between 0 and 1. A higher value means a stronger chance that the drug may cause the side effect. The model is trained by reducing prediction error using binary cross-entropy loss:
 $L = -\sum(y \cdot \log(p) + (1-y) \cdot \log(1-p))$

In this equation y is represented as the actual relationship label and p is represented as the predicted probability.

Link Prediction

Fig. 4. Link prediction showing possible connections between nodes.

Graph-based link prediction approaches have been used in earlier studies to identify hidden biomedical relationships and improve prediction accuracy [1], [7]. Using this formulation, the model learns patterns from the knowledge graph and predicts possible side effects for drugs. This mathematical framework helps transform biomedical data into a structured learning problem and supports graph neural network based prediction.

VI. GRAPH NEURAL NETWORK MODEL ARCHITECTURE

The Graph Neural Network architecture predicts possible drug side effects.

The model creates drug and adverse reaction representations through its drug-side effect interaction graph which shows their existing relationship. The network achieves accurate prediction by collecting information from linked nodes to process both nearby node connections and overall network design.

A. Graph Neural Network Overview

Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) are models used when data can be represented as a graph. In this type of data, items are connected to each other, such as drugs linked to diseases or side effects [5]. GNNs learn by using both the features of a node and the information from its connected neighbours. This helps the model understand relationships that may not be clear in normal table data [6]. Graph Convolutional Networks (GCN) are a popular type of GNN for predicting

links between nodes, such as drug–side effect relations [1]. Because these models consider connections between entities, they are useful in biomedical prediction tasks [7].

B. Message Passing and Node Representation Learning

In Graph Neural Networks, each node learns information from the nodes connected to it. This process is called message passing. Instead of using only its own features, each node updates its representation by combining information from its neighboring nodes. This helps the model understand how different biomedical entities such as drugs, diseases, and side effects are related to each other [5].

During each network layer, the node collects information from its connected neighbors and updates its feature values. By repeating this process across multiple layers, the model learns both direct and indirect relationships between nodes. For example, a drug may not be directly connected to a side effect, but it may still show a relationship through other intermediate nodes such as diseases or proteins [6].

The updated node values are called node embeddings. These embeddings are numerical representations that capture essential information about each node and its position in the graph. Node embeddings are later used to predict potential links between drugs and side effects. Similar message passing methods have been used in earlier graph-based biomedical studies to learn relationships between biological entities [1], [7].

This method allows the model to capture structural patterns present in the knowledge graph, improving the prediction of possible drug side effects.

C. Model Architecture

The proposed system uses a Graph Neural Network (GNN) to study relationships between drugs, diseases, and side effects using a constructed knowledge graph. Biomedical information often contains numerous connections among different entities such as drugs, proteins, and diseases. Representing this information as a graph helps maintain these relationships and allows the model to learn useful patterns from connected data [5].

1. Input Representation

The model takes a knowledge graph as input. Then this graph is created using drug names, meddra all se, drug action labels, drug disease labels, and drug symptom labels datasets. In the graph, nodes represent biomedical entities, and edges represent the relationships between them. Each node is converted into numerical form so that it can be used by the learning algorithm. Compared to normal table data, graph representation keeps the relationship information between entities more effectively [6].

2. Graph Construction

The knowledge graph is formed by combining the information from different datasets. Drugs are linked to the diseases they treat and also to the side effects they may produce. These links help the model understand how biomedical entities are related to each other. Graph structures are commonly used in biomedical research because they allow different types of information to combine within a single framework [7].

3. Graph Convolution Layers

Graph Convolutional Network (GCN) layers are used to learn features from the graph. In each layer, node information is updated by considering the features of neighboring nodes. This allows the model to learn both direct and indirect relationships. GCN models are often used in biomedical problems because they are able to capture patterns from connected data [1]. Activation functions such as ReLU are used between layers so that the model can learn more complex relationships between entities.

4. Node Embedding Layer

After passing through the graph convolution layers, the model produces node embeddings. These embeddings are numerical values that represent the characteristics of drugs, diseases, and side effects. The embeddings contain information about how nodes are connected in the graph. Such representations help the model compare nodes and identify possible relationships between them [8].

5. Link Prediction Layer

The link prediction layer is used to estimate whether a drug may be related to a particular side effect. The model checks similarity between node embeddings and produces a probability score. If the score is high, the model predicts that the drug may cause that side effect. Link prediction is commonly used in graph-based biomedical studies to identify unknown relationships between entities [5].

6. Model Training

The model trains using known relationships available in the knowledge graph. During training, it adjusts its parameters to reduce prediction error, using loss functions to measure how close the predicted results are to actual relationships. Similar graph learning methods have been used in previous studies to predict drug interactions and side effects [7].

Overall, the GNN architecture helps the system learn patterns from connected biomedical data. By using graph structure information, the model can identify possible side effects and support early analysis of drug safety.

VII. RESULTS AND PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

This section evaluates the proposed Graph Neural Network (GNN) model for predicting potential drug side effects. We measure the model's effectiveness using common classification metrics and compare its performance to traditional machine learning methods. The aim is to see if graph-based learning can better capture complex biomedical relationships than standard feature-based models.

A. Evaluation Metrics

We assess the model's performance using Accuracy, Area Under the Curve (AUC), and F1-score. The action classification accuracy is 0.5423, which indicates moderate classification performance considering the complexity of biomedical relationships.

The AUC value of **0.53** shows that the model is able to separate different classes reasonably well. The macro F1-score of 0.3544 indicates variation in performance between classes, especially when class sizes are different. The weighted F1-score of 0.5453 shows improved balance when class distribution is considered.

The side effect prediction F1-score (micro) is 0.5355, which indicates balanced performance between precision and recall. Overall, these values suggest that the model is able to learn meaningful patterns from graph-structured biomedical data.

B. Quantitative Performance Comparison

We compare the proposed GNN model with traditional machine learning methods, including Logistic Regression and Random Forest. These baseline models use tabular features, while the proposed method uses graph structure information that captures relationships between biomedical entities. The comparison results are shown in Table 2.

Model	Accuracy	F1-Score	AUC
Logistic Regression	0.43	0.49	0.72
Random Forest	0.52	0.52	0.68
Proposed GNN Model	0.53	0.54	0.74

Table 1. Quantitative performance comparison of machine learning models.

From the results, the Graph Neural Network shows slightly better performance compared to the baseline models across all evaluation measures. The improvement in AUC value indicates that the GNN model is able to better distinguish between drug-side effect relationships and unrelated pairs. This happens because graph-based learning considers connections between biomedical entities instead of treating each data point independently [5].

Traditional models like Logistic Regression and Random Forest mainly depend on feature values and do not fully use relationship information between drugs, diseases, and side effects. In contrast, the GNN model learns directly from the structure of the knowledge graph, where nodes represent biomedical entities and edges indicate their relationships. Learning from connected data helps the model capture patterns that may not be easily identified using standard machine learning methods [6].

Previous studies also show that graph-based approaches improve performance in biomedical prediction problems because biological entities are naturally interconnected [7].

The results indicate that using relational information through Graph Neural Networks can provide more reliable predictions for drug side effect analysis.

C. Confusion Matrix Analysis

The confusion matrix in Fig. 2 summarizes the prediction results by comparing actual labels with the predicted labels from the GNN model. The matrix contains 57,629 true negatives, 6,187 false positives, 8,258 false negatives, and 8,326 true positives. The large number of true negatives shows that the model correctly identifies most drug-side effect pairs that do not have a relationship.

The model also identifies 8,326 true positive cases, indicating that it can detect many valid drug-side effect associations. Some false negatives (8,258) are present, meaning a few actual side effects were not predicted by the model. However, overall, the model does a reasonable job distinguishing between related and unrelated pairs.

Fig. 5. Confusion matrix for the proposed GNN model.

This type of performance is useful in healthcare applications, as identifying possible adverse drug reactions in advance can help improve patient safety and support better clinical decisions.

D. Embedding Visualization

Dimensionality reduction was applied to convert the high-dimensional node embeddings generated by the GNN into a two-dimensional space using Principal Component Analysis (PCA). This transformation helps in visually examining how well the model captures relationships between different biological entities.

Fig. 6. 2D visualization of learned drug embeddings.

Fig. 6 illustrates the 2D distribution of embeddings belonging to five predicted classes: bacteria, fungus, human cell, virus, and other. Each point represents a learned embedding, and points with similar characteristics tend to appear closer to each other in the plot.

From the visualization, it can be observed that several groups form noticeable clusters. For example, many bacteria and fungus embeddings appear concentrated in specific regions, indicating that the model is able to capture meaningful structural similarities. The human cell class is spread across a wider area, suggesting more variation in its feature representation. A few virus samples appear more scattered, which may be due to limited data or diverse interaction patterns. The “other” class overlaps with multiple groups, showing that it shares features with several categories.

Overall, the plot indicates that the GNN successfully learns useful representations by preserving relationships between entities. Similar biological classes tend to appear closer in the embedding space, which demonstrates the effectiveness of the graph-based learning approach.

E. Probability Graph Analysis

Fig. 7. Side-effect probability scores predicted by the GNN model.

Fig. 7 shows the probability values of different side effects predicted by the proposed GNN model. Each bar in the graph represents the chance of a specific side effect occurring based on the relationships learned from the dataset.

The figure includes five side effects: dizziness, headache, nausea, rash, and vomiting. All the values are high and close to 1, meaning the model predicts a strong possibility for these side effects. Nausea has the highest value, indicating a stronger relationship than the others. Headache and vomiting also show high probabilities, suggesting similar behavior. Dizziness and rash have slightly lower values but still indicate a high chance of occurrence.

This graph helps in understanding how the model estimates the risk of each side effect. It clearly shows which effects are more likely and supports the evaluation of the prediction results. This visualization makes the output easier to interpret and useful for further medical or research analysis.

VIII. DISCUSSION AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

A. Discussion

The results obtained from the proposed Graph Neural Network model indicate that graph-based learning can effectively capture relationships between drugs, diseases, and side effects. Unlike traditional machine learning approaches that treat data as independent features, graph neural networks use the connections between biomedical entities to learn meaningful patterns. This allows the model to identify indirect relationships that may not be easily visible in tabular data. Previous studies have also shown that graph-based approaches improve prediction performance in biomedical problems because they utilize relational information present in biological networks [5], [6].

By combining multiple datasets into a knowledge graph, the model is able to learn from different types of biomedical relationships. Integrating drug–disease associations and drug–side effect relationships enables the model to better understand patterns that lead to adverse reactions. Similar approaches have been used in earlier research, where multi-source biomedical data improved the prediction capability of graph neural network models [1], [7].

The proposed approach also provides confidence scores for predicted side effects. These scores help estimate how strongly a side effect is associated with a drug. Such probability-based predictions are useful in supporting decision making during early stages of drug development. Graph-based link prediction methods have been widely used to identify unknown relationships between biomedical entities [5].

However, certain limitations were observed during the study. Biomedical datasets are often incomplete and imbalanced, meaning that some side effects occur less frequently than others. Some graph neural network models also require sufficient connectivity between nodes to learn meaningful embeddings. In cases where relationships between entities are limited, prediction performance may decrease. Similar challenges have been reported in previous studies involving graph-based biomedical learning [8].

Another limitation is that deep learning models require careful parameter tuning and sufficient training data. The reliability of predictions depends heavily on the quality and completeness of the datasets used. Missing or inconsistent information can hurt the learning process. Therefore, proper preprocessing and integration of biomedical data are crucial for achieving reliable prediction performance.

B. Future Directions

The proposed framework has multiple potential research directions which can lead to its better development.

1. Adding more biomedical datasets

In future work, more datasets such as protein interaction data and gene information can be included. Using more biological data may help the model understand drug behaviour better. Earlier studies show that combining different types of biomedical information can improve prediction results [7].

2. Using other graph neural network models

This work uses Graph Convolutional Networks, but other models like Graph Attention Networks can also be tested. These models give different importance to neighbouring nodes and may improve prediction quality. Similar approaches have been explored in recent graph-based biomedical studies [6].

3. Improving interpretability of predictions

In medical applications, it is important to understand why a model predicts a certain side effect. Future work can focus on methods that highlight which features or relationships influence the prediction. Explainable graph models have been discussed in previous research to make predictions easier to understand [8].

4. Handling imbalance in dataset

Some side effects appear very rarely in available datasets. Because of this, the model may not learn enough information about uncommon reactions. Future research can try different sampling or balancing methods to improve prediction for rare side effects.

5. Extending the model for drug repositioning

The same graph-based method can also be used to find new therapeutic uses for existing drugs. Graph-based methods are used in earlier studies to discover new relationships between drugs and diseases [6]. This can help reduce time and cost required for drug development.

IX. IMPLICATIONS AND LIMITATIONS

A. Practical Implications

The proposed Graph Neural Network model can support early identification of potential drug side effects, which is important during the initial stages of drug development. Detecting adverse reactions before clinical trials can help reduce risks, minimize experimental costs, and improve the overall efficiency of pharmaceutical research. Graph-based prediction methods have been successfully applied in biomedical studies to improve decision-making related to drug safety [5].

The use of a knowledge graph allows the integration of information from multiple biomedical datasets. This helps represent relationships among drugs, diseases, and side effects in a structured manner. Combining different sources of biomedical information improves understanding of drug behaviour and supports more reliable predictions [7].

Such a system can also assist researchers in identifying possible risks linked to existing drugs. Predicting side effects in advance may help reduce unexpected health complications and improve treatment safety. Graph neural network models have shown strong capability in analyzing complex biological relationships and supporting safer healthcare decisions [6].

In addition, the proposed framework may support drug discovery and drug repositioning studies by identifying new relationships between drugs and diseases. This can reduce both time and cost involved in developing new medicines.

Overall, the model provides a computational approach that helps researchers better understand drug interactions and identify potential safety concerns..

B. Limitations

Despite promising results, the model has certain limitations. The prediction quality largely depends on the completeness and reliability of biomedical datasets. Missing or inconsistent information may affect model performance. In addition, biomedical data often contains imbalance, where some side effects occur rarely, making them harder for the model to learn.

Graph neural networks also require sufficient relationships between nodes to learn effective embeddings. When the knowledge graph contains limited connections, prediction accuracy may decrease. Similar challenges have been reported in previous graph-based biomedical studies [5].

Model performance is also influenced by parameter selection, such as learning rate, number of layers, and embedding size. Furthermore, graph-based models may require higher computational resources when working with large datasets.

The current work uses a limited set of biomedical data. Including additional biological information such as gene interactions or protein networks may further improve prediction accuracy, as demonstrated in earlier studies [7].

Even with these limitations, the proposed approach provides a useful framework for analyzing relationships between drugs and side effects and supports early-stage risk assessment before experimental validation..

X. MATHEMATICAL ANALYSIS AND MODEL VALIDATION

A. Mathematical Analysis

In this work, we model the problem of predicting drug side effects using a graph representation. Biomedical data often contains relationships among drugs, diseases, and side effects. We can effectively show these connections using nodes and edges in a graph. Graph representation is useful because it keeps the relationship information between different biomedical entities instead of treating them separately [5].

Let the graph be written as:

$$G = (V, E)$$

where V represents the set of nodes and E is the set of edges connecting them. Each node stands for a biomedical entity like a drug, disease, or side effect, while edges illustrate the relationships between these entities. For instance, a connection might show that a drug treats a disease or is linked to a certain side effect.

The graph connections can be stored using an adjacency matrix:

$$A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$$

where n represents the total number of nodes. If two nodes are connected, the value is 1; otherwise, the value is 0.

Each node is represented using a feature vector:

$$X \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d}$$

where d represents the number of features. These features help the model learn information about each biomedical entity.

The Graph Convolutional Network (GCN) learns node features by combining information from neighboring nodes. During each layer, node information is updated using the following rule:

$$H^{(l+1)} = \sigma(\hat{A}H^{(l)}W^{(l)})$$

where

\hat{A} represents normalized adjacency matrix

$H^{(l)}$ will represents node features at layer l

$W^{(l)}$ will represents weight matrix

σ represents activation function

Initially, node features are given as:

$$H^{(0)} = X$$

After multiple layers, the model generates node embeddings. These embeddings contain information about node relationships present in the graph. Graph-based mathematical models are commonly used in biomedical prediction tasks because they help capture interactions between biological entities [6].

To predict whether a drug is related to a side effect, link prediction is performed. The similarity between two nodes is calculated using dot product:

$$Score(u, v) = \sigma(h_u^T h_v)$$

where

h_u represents embedding of drug node

h_v represents embedding of side effect node

The sigmoid function converts the value into probability between 0 and 1. Higher values indicate stronger relationship between nodes.

The model is trained using the binary cross entropy loss:

$$L = -\sum(y \log(p) + (1 - y) \log(1 - p))$$

where

y will represents actual value

p will represents predicted value

Similar mathematical approaches have been used in earlier studies for predicting drug interactions using graph-based learning [1], [7].

B. Model Validation

We perform model validation to assess how accurately the system predicts relationships between drugs and side effects. We divide the available dataset into training and testing sets. The model first learns patterns from the training data and then undergoes evaluation using the testing data to measure its ability to generalize to new examples.

We measure performance using evaluation metrics like Accuracy, AUC, and F1-score. Accuracy shows how many predictions are correct out of total predictions. AUC measures how well the model separates related and unrelated drug-side effect pairs. F1-score considers both precision and recall, which is useful when the dataset contains imbalance. These evaluation measures are commonly used in graph-based biomedical prediction models [6]. Previous research shows that graph learning methods improve prediction when relationships between entities are considered [5].

However, the effectiveness of the predictions relies on the quality of the dataset and the number of connections among biomedical entities. Limited or incomplete relationships can lower model performance, which is a common challenge in graph-based biomedical learning [8].

Overall, the mathematical formulation and validation process show that graph neural network models provide a valuable framework for exploring relationships between drugs and side effects. This approach helps identify possible risks and supports early stage drug safety analysis.

XI. IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS

A. Software Environment

The proposed model is implemented using Python because it provides good support for machine learning and graph-based data processing. PyTorch framework is used for building and training the Graph Neural Network model. PyTorch Geometric library is used to implement graph convolution operations and handle graph structured data efficiently. Pandas and NumPy libraries are used for preprocessing the biomedical datasets and performing numerical operations.

The user interface is developed using Streamlit, which allows simple interaction with the model. Users can enter the name

of a drug and obtain predicted side effects. RapidFuzz library is used to match input drug names with dataset values when there are small spelling differences.

The implementation is executed on a system with standard computing resources. GPU support can be used to reduce training time when large datasets are involved. Similar software environments are commonly used in graph-based biomedical prediction studies [6].

B. Model Configuration

The Graph Neural Network model uses Graph Convolutional Network (GCN) layers to learn patterns from a constructed knowledge graph. This graph combines information from several biomedical datasets, including drug names, MedDRA side effect data, drug action labels, drug-disease relationships, and drug-symptom associations. Each node in the graph represents a biomedical entity and contains feature values.

The model consists of multiple graph convolution layers followed by node embedding generation. These embeddings represent structural information present in the graph. Activation functions such as ReLU are used between layers to allow the model to learn non-linear relationships between nodes.

Important parameters, such as the number of GCN layers, hidden dimension size, learning rate, and the number of training iterations, are chosen through experimentation to ensure stable performance. These parameters are selected experimentally to obtain stable performance. Similar configurations have been used in previous studies involving graph neural network models for biomedical prediction tasks [1], [7].

C. Training Procedure

The training process uses known drug-side effect relationships found in the knowledge graph. During training, node features are passed through graph convolution layers to generate embeddings. The link prediction layer estimates the probability of relationship between drug nodes and side effect nodes.

Binary cross-entropy loss measures the difference between predicted values and actual relationships. During training, the optimizer adjusts the model parameters to decrease prediction error. Training continues until the loss becomes stable.

To assess the model's effectiveness, the dataset is split into training and testing sets. The trained model is tested on unseen data using evaluation metrics such as accuracy, AUC, and F1-score. Similar training procedures are used in graph-based biomedical learning studies [5].

D. Reproducibility and Experimental Stability

To maintain reproducibility, the same preprocessing steps and parameter settings are used during multiple training runs. Random initialization values are controlled using fixed seed values so that similar results can be obtained when the experiment is repeated.

Experimental stability is observed by monitoring loss values and evaluation metrics during training. Consistent performance across multiple runs indicates that the model learns stable patterns from the knowledge graph.

Using structured datasets and controlled training conditions helps ensure reliable model behavior. Reproducibility is important in biomedical research so that results can be verified and compared with other studies [8].

XII. CONCLUSION

In this work, we present an approach based on a Graph Neural Network to predict possible drug side effects using biomedical knowledge graph data. The model combines information from drug names, meddra all se, drug action labels, drug disease labels, and drug symptom labels datasets to represent relationships between biomedical entities in the form of a graph. This structure helps preserve connections between drugs, diseases, and side effects, allowing the model to learn meaningful patterns from relational data.

Graph Convolutional Network layers are used to generate node embeddings that capture structural information present in the knowledge graph. The link prediction approach helps estimate the probability of relationships between drugs and side effects. Compared to traditional machine learning methods, graph-based learning is more suitable for biomedical problems because it considers relationships between entities rather than treating features independently [5], [6].

The results show that integrating multiple biomedical datasets helps improve understanding of drug behaviour and supports prediction of possible adverse drug reactions. Similar observations have been reported in earlier studies where graph-based learning methods demonstrated improved performance in drug interaction and side effect prediction tasks [1], [7].

The proposed approach also provides confidence scores for predicted side effects, which may help researchers identify potential risks before clinical testing. Early prediction of side effects may reduce drug development cost and improve patient safety. Graph neural network models have been widely applied in biomedical research because they are capable of learning complex biological relationships [8].

Although the model's performance relies on data quality and the availability of relationships between entities, the proposed framework offers a structured way to analyze biomedical data. The study demonstrates that graph-based

learning can be useful in supporting drug safety analysis and identifying possible risks at an early stage.

Overall, the proposed method shows that Graph Neural Networks can be effectively applied to predict drug side effects using knowledge graph representation. This approach may support further research in drug safety evaluation and assist in development of safer medicines.

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